

A simple paper chromatographic technique for detection of different types of histones in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states *in vitro*

S. N. Upadhyay^{a*}, Ram Pal Singh^a, V. S. Bhatnagar^a and H. C. Goel^b

^aDepartment of Radiation Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Radiation Biology, Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences, Lucknow Marg, Delhi-110 054, India

Fax : 91-011-3919505

Manuscript received 17 April 2001, revised 24 September 2001, accepted 12 November 2001

Paper chromatographic technique has been employed to detect low levels (20–25 µg/ml) of H₁, H₃ and H₄ histones under physiological pH range in the native, heat denatured and gamma irradiated states (10–50 Gy). The R_f values obtained for these histones under different experimental conditions have rendered insight about the configurational alterations.

Many techniques have evolved for detection of proteins by analytical methods (e.g. size exclusion chromatography¹, gel electrophoresis², HPLC³). Separation of proteins is often done by HPLC³, affinity chromatography⁴ and thin layer ion-exchange chromatography^{5,6}, which can identify amino acids down up to 0.01–0.8 µg/ml concentration⁷. Three different histones, namely, H₁⁸, H₃⁹ and H₄¹⁰ are constituents of nucleosome and have definite biological roles. Hence their detection in small amounts is important. Paper chromatographic technique which is very simple, inexpensive but semiquantitative as compared to the techniques mentioned earlier, has enabled us to detect these histones up to 20–25 µg/ml.

Results and Discussion

H₁ histone solution (pH range 6.40–6.90) in the unirradiated state showed increased R_f value in phosphate buffer (0.50–0.30) compared to that in SSC buffer (0.32, 0.15 and 0.11). Upon heat denaturation, R_f values compared to the controls in (0.35 and 0.15) phosphate buffer and (0.28 and 0.19) SSC buffer. For some solutions for a dose range of 10–50 Gy, pH range 6.40–6.90, R_f (yellow) remained fairly constant but R_f (violet) decreased with increasing radiation dose in phosphate buffer (Table 1). In SSC buffer, R_f values did not change to any substantial extent for the same dose range (Table 1).

The amino acid composition¹¹ and configurational aspect⁸ of H₁ histone is known. In phosphate buffer, cylindrical configuration is favored whereas in SSC buffer coiled configuration is favored as the counter-ions (e.g.

Na⁺, Cl⁻) bind with the carboxylic acid groups of amino acids dissociated from H₁ histone. Cylindrical configuration favors higher R_f value but coiled configuration favors lower R_f value due to their variation in the overall charge distribution along the molecule. Thermal denaturation unfolded the molecule in both the solvents thereby making the movements slower. So, R_f values decreased. H₁ histone has been reported to be sensitive to gamma radiation dose up to 50 Gy¹². Probable amino acids released from H₁ histone under different experimental conditions (irradiation) are proline, lysine, alanine, valine, glutamine and glycine. So, when globular part of the molecule gets altered with dose (in phosphate buffer) that could be detected by R_f value. Binding of counter-ions to H₁ histone did not allow the radiation induced changes detectable in SSC buffer (Table 1).

Table 1. R_f values of H₁ histones under different experimental conditions*

Concn. = 20 µg/ml, dose rate = 0.009 Gy/s, pH = 6.40–6.90		Gamma irradiated dose (Gy)				
Un-irradiated	Heat-dinatured	10	20	30	40	50
0.1 M Phosphate buffer :						
R _f = 0.30	R _f = 0.15	R _f = 0.16	R _f = 0.15	R _f = 0.14	R _f = 0.11	R _f = 0.09
violet	violet	violet	violet	violet	violet	violet
R _f = 0.50	R _f = 0.35	–	R _f = 0.34	R _f = 0.37	R _f = 0.38	R _f = 0.35
yellow	yellow	–	yellow	yellow	yellow	yellow
0.15 M SSC buffer :						
R _f = 0.15	R _f = 0.19	R _f = 0.14	R _f = 0.13	R _f = 0.14	R _f = 0.15	R _f = 0.16
violet	violet	violet	violet	violet	violet	violet
R _f = 0.32	R _f = 0.28	–	R _f = 0.33	R _f = 0.27	R _f = 0.25	R _f = 0.30
yellow	yellow	–	yellow	yellow	yellow	yellow

* n = 5; standard deviation : ±0.005–0.010.

H₃ histone in phosphate and SSC buffers in the unirradiated state did not show significant variation in R_f (pH range 6.50–7.05). Thermal denaturation increased the R_f values in both the solvents compared to control. Up to 50 Gy, H₃ histone solutions in SSC buffer did not show significant variation in R_f values, but it increased in phosphate buffer (Table 2).

Table 2. R_f values of H₃ histones under different experimental conditions*

Concn. = 20 µg/ml, dose rate=0.0094 Gy/s, pH = 6.50–7.05

Un-irradiated	Heat-denatured	Gamma irradiated dose (Gy)				
		10	20	30	40	50
0.1 M Phosphate buffer :						
R _f = 0.15 violet	R _f = 0.17 violet	R _f = 0.21 violet	R _f = 0.23 violet	R _f = 0.24 violet	R _f = 0.18 violet	R _f = 0.19 violet
R _f = 0.33 crimson red	R _f = 0.37 crimson red	R _f = 0.34 crimson red	R _f = 0.35 crimson red	R _f = 0.36 crimson red	R _f = 0.37 crimson red	R _f = 0.43 crimson red
0.15 M SSC buffer :						
R _f = 0.18 violet	R _f = 0.20 violet	R _f = 0.15 violet	R _f = 0.20 violet	R _f = 0.13 violet	R _f = 0.16 violet	R _f = 0.16 violet
R _f = 0.33 violet + blue	R _f = 0.43 violet	R _f = 0.28 violet + blue	R _f = 0.35 violet + blue	R _f = 0.30 crimson red	R _f = 0.35 crimson red	R _f = 0.30 crimson red

*n = 5; standard deviation : ±0.005–0.015.

The amino acid composition of H₃ histone is known¹³. Heat-denaturation favored condensed cylindrical configuration. This increased R_f value. For SSC buffer, counter-ion condensation is more compared to phosphate buffer. Surface charge distribution in these two buffers also varied. Compared to H₁ histone, H₃ histone is relatively insensitive to radiation dose¹⁴. Probable amino acids released from H₃ histone under different experimental conditions (irradiation and heat denaturation) were glutamine, glycine, isoleucine, valine, serine and alanine. This has been reflected in their R_f values (Tables 1 and 2).

The R_f values of H₄ histone did not differ much in phosphate or SSC buffer. But thermal denaturation increased the values to an appreciable degree. When H₄ histone solution was exposed to increasing gamma radiation dose in phosphate buffer, R_f value slowly decreased, but no significant change was observed in SSC buffer under identical condition. The pH range was 6.50–7.05 under different experimental conditions.

The amino acid composition and configurational aspects of H₄ histone are known¹³. Upon heat denaturation, the configuration of H₄ histone got transformed from coil to helix form to some extent. Radiation dose had an uncoiling effect on the configuration of H₄ histone in phosphate buff-

er. But in SSC buffer, it did not take place due to counter-ion condensation. These have been reflected in their R_f values. Solvent effect on the radiation induced changes in H₄ histone reported by us¹⁴ supports this view. Probable amino acids released from H₄ histone under different experimental conditions are lysine, histidine, valine, arginine, isoleucine and proline. The different amino acids under the same experimental condition show different colors and R_f values¹⁵. By matching the colors and R_f values the different probable amino acids released from different histones as a result of radiation dose were identified.

Compared to control at very low dose of 10 Gy, there has not been a marked change in the R_f values of H₁, H₃ and H₄ histones prepared in 0.15 M SSC buffer (Tables 1–3). Counter-ions present in this buffer is quite high (e.g. Na⁺, Cl⁻ etc.) At a low dose, radiation reduced free radicals interact mostly with these counter-ions. No significant configurational change has occurred in these histones. So R_f values have not changed.

Table 3. R_f values of H₄ histones under different experimental conditions*

Concn. = 20 µg/ml, dose rate = 0.0094 Gy/s, pH = 6.50–7.05

Un-irradiated	Heat-denatured	Gamma irradiated dose (Gy)				
		10	20	30	40	50
0.1 M Phosphate buffer :						
R _f = 0.10 violet	R _f = 0.50 crimson red	R _f = 0.21 violet	R _f = 0.18 violet	R _f = 0.15 violet	R _f = 0.13 violet	R _f = 0.12 violet
R _f = 0.23 crimson red		R _f = 0.16 crimson red	R _f = 0.16 crimson red	R _f = 0.12 crimson red	R _f = 0.10 crimson red	R _f = 0.09 crimson red
0.15 M SSC buffer :						
R _f = 0.13 violet	R _f = 0.31 violet	R _f = 0.13 violet	R _f = 0.17 violet	R _f = 0.14 violet	R _f = 0.13 violet	R _f = 0.15 violet

*n = 5; standard deviation : ±0.005–0.020.

Experimental

Histones (H₁, M.W. 21500; H₃, M.W. 15324; H₄, M.W. 11282) (Sigma); ninhydrin, *n*-butanol, acetic acid (all Qualigen) were used. Other chemicals were of E. Merck. Whatman chromatographic paper was used.

Any of the histones (concentration range 20–25 µg/ml) were applied on Whatman chromatographic paper, then allowed to dry with a stream of air and placed inside the chromatographic tank containing a solvent mixture (e.g. acetone : *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water :: 35 : 35 : 10 : 20, v/v). Histones were prepared in either 0.15 M standard saline citrate buffer or in 0.1 M phosphate buffer. The solvent mixture was allowed to come up to a distance of 10 cm

Note

from the point of application. The chromatograms were dried and 0.4% ninhydrin solution in acetone was sprayed. After drying with a stream of hot air the chromatograms were kept in an oven for 70–80° for 0.5 h. The color developed was marked and R_f values determined. pH values were obtained by adding 0.01 N NaOH or 0.01 N HCl. Heat denaturation of the histone was done by keeping the experimental solution at 90–100° for 2 h. Gamma irradiation was done in a Gamma Cell 220 of Atomic Energy of Canada. Dose rates were determined by FBX dosimetry¹⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. T. Lazar Mathew, Director, for taking interest in this work and giving permission to publish it. Thanks are due to Sh. Ashok Kumar Sharma, for providing data processing support.

References

1. J. G. de la Torre, S. Navarro, M. C. Lopez-Martinez, F. G. Diaz and J. J. Lopez-Cascales, *Biophys. J.*, 1994, **67**, 530.
2. J. J. Ewbank and T. E. Creiton, *Biochemistry*, 1993, **32**, 3677.
3. G. Kreil, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1994, **269**, 10967.
4. T. R. Hupp, D. W. Meek, C. A. Midley and D. P. Lane, *Cell*, 1992, **71**, 875.
5. B. Friguet, A. Fedorov, A. A. Serganov, A. Navon and M. E. Goldberg, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1993, **210**, 344.
6. Q. Luo, J. D. Andrade and K. D. Kaldweld, *J. Chromatogr., Sect. A*, 1998, **816**, 97.
7. S. Laskar, A. Sinhababu and K. M. Hazra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 49.
8. A. P. Wolfe, *Int. J. Biochem. Cell. Biol.*, 1997, **29**, 1463.
9. G. De Murcia and M. De Murcia, *Trends Biochem. Sci.*, 1994, **19**, 172.
10. M. Kozurkova, E. Misurova and K. Kropacrova, *Mechanisms ageing develop.*, 1993, **72**, 37.
11. P. G. Hatman, G. E. Chapman, T. Moss and E. M. Bradbury, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1977, **77**, 45.
12. S. N. Upadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 424.
13. C. Von Holt, W. N. Strikland, W. F. Brandt and M. S. Strikland, *FEBS Lett.*, 1979, **100**, 201.
14. S. N. Upadhyay, "Proceedings of the International Conference on Chemistry and 36th Annual Convention of Chemists", Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1999, Abstr. no. Phy 109.
15. J. Sharma, *Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **66**, 67.
16. S. N. Upadhyay, J. Singh and A. R. Reddy, *Indian J. Radiol.*, 1982, **36**, 141.

